

What's in a word? Or in an armamentarium?

A. Shah Idil*

I was perusing Brown's 1998 revision of the epilepsy needs document for the UK [1] when I came across a word unfamiliar to my engineer's eyes on p. 439: "armamentarium".

I asked the Oxford English Dictionary to define the word for me, and it returned to my surprise: "no exact matches". It did, however, suggest an alternative with two extra letters: "armamentarium" (from the Latin *armamentum* - "arsenal"). This had the meaning: "the medicines, equipment, and techniques available to a medical practitioner" – much more in line with a paragraph regarding new trends in anti-epileptics.

I thought perhaps Brown had made a simple mistake, but a quick search on PubMed in 2025 delivered 121 articles with the same non-word. Google Scholar gave me 2,970! There have already been a few papers published in 2025 containing "armamentarium", with phrases such as "the therapeutic armamentarium", and "the medical armamentarium" [2]–[4]. If one goes back far enough, one can even find 5 papers with the typographical error in the title itself [5]–[9]!

I believe the error started from one of these five, specifically with Fox's 1968 paper, with not just one but two typographical errors in the title: "Endodontic armamentarium for the genral practitioner" [sic]. I cannot find the full paper, or even an abstract, so I cannot say if he struggled with spelling or had a particularly poor editor. The error likely propagated from there.

After a brief investigation, I found that there is indeed such a word as "armamentarium" – just not in English. It is the accusative singular of the Latin word *armamentarius*, meaning a herdsman, or a cowboy [10].

So, let us then all not be "cowboys", and be careful in our use of technical medical terminology. The consequences may not always be so harmless.

20TH OF NOVEMBER, 2025.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Brown, T. Betts, P. Crawford, B. Hall, S. Shorvon, and S. Wallace, "Epilepsy needs revisited: a revised epilepsy needs document for the UK," 1998.
- [2] D. Pfister, P. Paffenholz, C. Rieger and A. Heidenreich, "Reduction of systemic chemotherapy by primary retroperitoneal lymph node dissection in low volume metastatic seminoma." *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, vol. 43, 626-626, 2025.
- [3] A Bourreille, J Kierkus, F Corallo, W Reinish, on behalf of the CoTikiS study group, "OP36 Lusvertikimab, a first-in-class IL7 receptor antagonist, in moderate to severe Ulcerative Colitis: results of a multicenter, randomized, placebo-controlled phase II study", *Journal of Crohn's and Colitis*, Volume 19, Issue Supplement 1, January 2025, Pages i71–i72.
- [4] T. Hilser, V. Darr, J. Bedke, P. Ivanyi, N. Klümper, M. Eckstein, K. Schlack and V. Grünwald, V., "Treatment of advanced or metastatic Urothelial Cancer." *Oncology Research and Treatment*, 2025.
- [5] J. Forcillo and L. P. Perrault, "Armentarium of topical hemostatic products in cardiovascular surgery: An update," *Transfus. Apher. Sci.*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 26–31, Feb. 2014.
- [6] N. Shanmugam and R. Liew, "The implantable loop recorder-an important addition to the armentarium in the management of unexplained syncope.," *Ann. Acad. Med. Singapore*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 115–24, Mar. 2012.
- [7] T. Mettang, B. Krumme, J. Bohler, and A. Roeckel, "Pentoxifylline as treatment for uraemic pruritus an addition to the weak armentarium for a common clinical symptom?," *Nephrol. Dial. Transplant.*, vol. 22, no. 9, pp. 2727–2728, Jun. 2007.
- [8] F. Lioté, "[Armentarium and strategies for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis].," *Rev. Prat.*, vol. 55, no. 19, pp. 2146–60, Dec. 2005.
- [9] R. Z. Fox and G. L. Hardy, "Endodontic armentarium for the genral practitioner.," *Dent. Dig.*, vol. 74, no. 11, pp. 462–7, Nov. 1968.
- [10] Wiktionary contributors. (n.d.). Armentarius. Wiktionary. Retrieved June 3, 2025, from <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/armamentarius>

*A. Shah Idil (corresponding author, email: a.shahidil@ucl.ac.uk) is with the Implanted Devices Group, University College London, London, UK.